

Harnessing spatial thinking to support mathematics teaching and learning

Aidan Roche¹, Gavin Duffy¹, Aoibhinn Ní Shúilleabháin²

¹ Technological University Dublin, ² University College Dublin

There is a growing consensus that spatial thinking is fundamental in how students conceive, express and perform mathematics. Decades of research show that building spatial skills yields measurable impacts on learning. This paper highlights however that the translation of research into explicit and systematic classroom practices to support spatial thinking in post-primary mathematics is not widespread. The aim of this paper is to: present a rationale for spatially enhancing mathematics curricula and pedagogy; to consider some existing tools and frameworks in the field; and to highlight the need for research that develops our understanding of effective practice that promotes spatial thinking in the mathematics classroom.

Irish Post-Primary mathematics: Should more focus be placed on spatial reasoning?

Spatial thinking or spatial reasoning (SR) is of growing importance in our technological world (Diezmann & Lowrie, 2012). SR involves the location and movement of objects and ourselves, either mentally or physically, in space. It concerns a considerable number of concepts, tools and processes (NRC, 2006). Three spatial skills that have been consistently studied in the literature are mental rotation, spatial orientation and spatial visualisation (Frick, 2019). These spatial abilities are malleable. Uttal et al. (2013) performed a meta-analysis examining 217 spatial training studies over a 25-year period and concluded that spatial training is an effective means for improving SR in people of all ages and across a variety of training techniques. There is also evidence that SR can also be developed through exposure to spatially rich learning experiences (Reilly et al., 2017). Developing SR has both moral and economic implications. Firstly, because it may mitigate against a spatial ability gender gap that exists to the disadvantage of females (Halpern, 2020), and secondly given that spatial ability is a strong predictor of future career choice (Wai et al., 2009) SR development is likely to improve gender equality p-STEM fields (Sorby et al., 2018).

Figure 1

Leaving Certificate Higher Level Mathematics Question 9, Paper 2, 2015

At a later hole, Joan's first shot lands at the point G , on ground that is sloping downwards, as shown. A vertical tree, $[CE]$, 25 metres high, stands between G and the hole. The distance, $|GC'|$, from the ball to the bottom of the tree is also 25 metres.

The angle of elevation at G to the top of the tree, E , is θ , where $\theta = \tan^{-1}(1/2)$.

The height of the top of the tree above the horizontal, GD , is h metres and $|GD| = d$ metres.

(i) Write d and $|CD|$ in terms of h .

Researchers have long been aware that spatial ability and mathematics are connected (MacFarlane Smith, 1964). “The relation between spatial ability and mathematics is so well

established that it no longer makes sense to ask whether they are related.” (Mix & Cheng, 2012, p. 206). A study by Hawes et al. (2019) found that children’s numerical and spatial skills collectively explained 84% of the variance in mathematics achievement. The emerging consensus is that spatial thinking plays a fundamental role in how people conceive, express, and perform mathematics (Hawes & Ansari, 2020). For example, the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (2000) recommends the use of visual representations as an instructional tool and diagrams are extensively used in mathematics textbooks and examination questions (figure 1). Taking advantage of visual representations makes good sense because students answer more word problems correctly when the problem is accompanied with a diagram (Hembree, 1992). However, it is also likely that students would benefit if they developed their representation comprehension skills given that they are a strong predictor of student learning in mathematics (Pantzarria et al. 2009) and because without support students often struggle to correctly interpret diagrams (Kozhevnikov et al., 2007). Giofrè et al. (2012) showed that the academic achievement of post-primary school geometry students was strongly related to their visuospatial working memory. Harris et al. (2020) connect differences in mathematical problem solving as a function of SR and mathematics content, in this study spatial factors accounted for 32% of the variance in grade 8 mathematics scores, and again this was particularly evident in the area of geometry. While both Stieff (2013) and Mix et al. (2016) argue that it may be particularly important to provide students with spatial scaffolding when students are learning a novel mathematical concept. Other research indicates that SR may even be required for mathematical reasoning (Cheng & Mix, 2014).

Aware of the strong connection between SR and mathematics Bishop (1980, p. 267) asks: “How much responsibility should mathematics teachers take for the training and teaching of spatial abilities?” This question is deserving of due consideration. In the US “learning to think spatially” is a key goal of education across school curricula (NRC, 2006) but in Ireland research supporting SR development has yet to meaningfully impact on our post-primary mathematics curricula. While “learning to think and communicate numerically and spatially” is a goal of the primary level curriculum it is omitted from post-primary mathematics curricula (NCCA, 2017, p.12) and it is notable there isn’t any reference to “spatial” in the Key Skills of Junior Cycle curricula reform and rationale document (NCCA, 2015).

Two strategies for harnessing spatial thinking to support mathematical learning

If we accept the strong evidence linking spatial thinking skills and mathematical success, the key question for researchers and educators naturally arises: How can spatial thinking research findings be translated into classroom practice to improve learning? Newcombe’s (2017) OECD working paper responds with two strategies for harnessing spatial thinking to support STEM learning. Strategy 1 involves direct training of spatial skills and Strategy 2 involves spatialising the curriculum, using tools suited to spatial thinking.

Strategy 1: Train spatial skills

For most people who hear about the link between spatial skills and mathematical learning, the obvious implication might be that we should train spatial skills. Diezmann and Lowrie (2012) advocate that spatial thinking requires explicit instruction. There is merit in this approach. Sorby et al. (2018) have shown that spatial skills instruction improves spatial cognition and boosts STEM related performance while others such as Cheng and Mix (2014) have demonstrated that training effects in spatial tasks are transferable to mathematics and calculation skills. However, a challenge for Strategy 1 remains that it requires adding more components to an already crowded curriculum or finding time for a new programme in an already-packed timetable. It may be difficult to find teachers or departments willing to take responsibility for or have the expertise to deliver this new material in schools.

Strategy 2: Spatialising the curriculum

Although it may still require curriculum development and professional development support for teachers, Strategy 2 has the great advantage that it offers the potential to support effective teaching and learning while developing SR at the same time. Spatial thinking is not an add-on to curricula, but rather an approach to thinking fundamental to the interpretation of graphics and complementary to mathematical and logical thinking (Barwise & Etchemendy, 1991). Though there are not many research examples specifically relating to spatialising post-primary mathematics curricula, a recent Australian project that demonstrated positive outcomes engaged middle school children in spatially enhanced mathematical learning activities and found that they outperformed the control classes in spatial reasoning (Lowrie et al., 2018). Syahputra (2013) also demonstrated that students' spatial ability can be improved by learning mathematics using a realistic mathematics education (RME) approach characterised by: the use of real or imagined context; the use of models; the connection between and between mathematical topics; the use of interactive methods; and appreciation of variations in answers and student contributions. Woolcott et al., (2020) recognise that SR is a potentially powerful but under-utilised bridging mechanism between real-world experiences and mathematics teaching and learning. This is because mathematical concept formation is connected to our interaction with the three-dimensional world in both a mathematical and non-mathematical way.

Newcombe et al. (2019) suggest that specific spatial skills may support specific mathematical exercises, in which case intervention should focus on the relevant spatial skills, however mathematics learning may be facilitated overall by a general spatial way of thinking, what has been called a spatial turn of mind. There are already some powerful tools that might support this spatial turn of mind for mathematical learning. For Newcombe (2017) these include: the use of symbolic systems such as spatial language and visual systems for communicating information, analogical learning, and learning that is grounded in embodied experience of the world. Collectively, the various tools allow us to leverage the spatial-mathematics connection, in which we “strive to incorporate spatial skills into the curriculum efficiently and pragmatically” (Newcombe, 2017, p. 24). A practical guide for mathematics

teachers to make more effective use of spatial teaching techniques in the classroom is Paying Attention to Spatial Reasoning (PATSR) (Ministry of Education in Ontario, 2014). It recognises that spatial reasoning is not a separate strand of mathematics, nor is it confined to geometry but rather that it is a process that can support learning and communicating across all strands. It asks a question that is of central importance here: How do we get started bringing awareness and development of spatial reasoning into teaching practise? It identifies nine specific ways to promote and scaffold SR in mathematics lessons using what this paper will refer to as “spatial enhancements” (SEs): (i) Teachers need to understand what spatial thinking is, and think of ways to support it within the content that they are teaching, (ii) Emphasise the strand of geometry and spatial sense, (iii) Emphasise spatial language, (iv) Encourage visualisation strategies, (v) Emphasise and celebrate visual displays of data, (vi) Use gestures and encourage students to gesture, (vii) Provide meaningful opportunities to investigate mathematical concepts and problems using manipulatives, (viii) Provide playful opportunities for students to exercise their spatial reasoning, and (ix) Take advantage of technology to promote spatial reasoning. Though each of these SEs are supported with by research further work is required to understand their particular role in a cohesive strategic approach to spatialising teaching and learning. This short paper can’t address all of these SEs but of particular importance in the current Irish is perhaps the recommendation to place emphasis on geometry.

Emphasise strands of geometry and spatial sense

Though “much of the thinking that is required in higher mathematics is spatial in nature” (Jones 2001, p. 55) Newcombe et al. (2019) recognises that spatial reasoning is a particularly strong contributor to mathematics achievement in the strand of geometry. This may be of particular interest to Irish post-primary educators because geometry is a relative weakness among our students. In TIMSS 2019, as in previous TIMSS assessments, geometry was the subscale in which Second Year students from Ireland score significantly lower than our countries overall mathematics score with a gender gap in favour of males on this subscale (Perkins & Clerkin, 2020). This is consistent with the performance of 15-year-old Irish students in “Space and shape” PISA tests (Clerkin et al., 2016). This weakness has also been identified in the Chief Examiners report (2015) noting that at higher level candidates struggled with questions from the geometry strand “in particular co-ordinate geometry and the construction of a triangle” (DES, 2015, p.15). It has been noted in the past that geometry is getting less time and attention in the classroom than other mathematics topics and less than the international average (Clerkin, Perkins & Chubb, 2018). It is perhaps fair to say that geometry is deserving of renewed attention for a number of reasons outlined above.

Developing a framework for spatialising mathematics curricula:

Strategy 2 requires that tools suitable for spatialising the curriculum would be developed. There is a shortage of systematic guides for teachers who wish to optimise spatially rich approaches in their classrooms. Gagnier and Fisher (2020) present a seven step Knowledge Translation Framework (KTF) to guide the infusion of SR research into science

curricula. This offers a framework that could potentially be adapted to mathematics education (figure 2).

Figure 2

Knowledge Translation framework Gagnier and Fisher, 2020

The development of this framework is a substantial and complex task. Phase 3 of the KTF requires the creation of research translation, implementation and refinement tools that support the systematic translation of SEs into the curriculum, because this relates directly to classroom practice, resources and pedagogy it is of particular interest to teachers of mathematics. Gagnier and Fisher (2020) created instructional supports including example lesson plans, a spatial word bank poster and SE icons for science education. Similar supports are required for mathematics educators. Using the research outlined in this paper ten spatial tools or SE scaffolds for mathematics have been identified and icons representing these strategies have been created (figure 3).

Figure 3

Spatial enhancement icons for mathematics

These SE scaffolds include: being particular about spatial language; using physical gesture; encouraging sketching, constructions and graphing; promoting visualisation strategies; engaging meaningfully with the spatial properties of visual representations; incorporating spatial contexts into mathematical tasks; using manipulatives and models; emphasising geometry; promoting spatial activities; and using DS and technology to engage students with dynamic spatial representations. Embedding SEs that promote SR into lesson planning, practice and assessment would add focus and support a systematic approach to spatialising mathematics teaching and learning. While there is some research supporting each

of these SEs more is required if we are to understand how to effectively combine them to shape mathematics curricula and pedagogy.

Conclusion

Mathematics teaching and learning would be enhanced if educators recognised the benefits of promoting SR in mathematics and found effective ways of doing it.

“It is likely enough that spatial intelligence is an important element in STEM success that we should use this idea in designing curricula, training teachers, setting goals and developing assessments, while simultaneously evaluating the effectiveness of the efforts and continuing basic research on the mechanisms” (Newcombe 2017 p.37).

Newcombe’s OECD paper (2017) proposes two worthy approaches for exploiting this finding Strategy 1 is to directly train students in spatial skills and Strategy 2 involves spatialising mathematics curricula using tools that support spatial thinking. Though it might seem ideal to pursue both strategies in parallel further research is required to understand how to effectively and efficiently do this and there exist challenges to implementing each strategy. To effectively realise Strategy 2 a systematic framework that translates research into practice (KTF) will need to be developed along with professional development that promotes teachers’ understanding of the important role of SR in mathematic learning, up-skills teachers to effectively embed spatial enhancements (SEs) into teaching and learning and perhaps to develop teachers own SR abilities. Research has identified a number of practical SEs that could be used to scaffold the development of SR and embed spatially rich approaches into classroom practice. These offer potential for the development of curricula and effective pedagogy but require further research to help educators understand how to use and combine these tools collectively to shape the curriculum. There are many questions that remain to be answered as literature provides little practical advice on: How often SEs should be used? Is a combination of SEs more effective than using one in a lesson? How frequently SEs should be used in a lesson? Which spatial enhancements best support the learning of specific mathematical content? Will it take more time to cover the curriculum using spatially enhanced lessons? Does the inclusion of SEs facilitate conceptual understanding or procedural fluency? And, are there specific considerations for diverse learners?

Mechanisms by which spatial skills training can promote mathematical thinking are still not well understood (Young et al., 2018). If we knew more about these mechanisms, educators would be better positioned to appropriately use and develop spatially rich approaches and utilise students’ spatial skills to aid mathematical learning and develop framework for spatialising mathematics. A promising avenue for future work is not just to support spatial thinking in general to show students can use this kind of thinking to solve particular kinds of mathematical problems (Casey, 2004). Also, little is known about the teachers’ current competence and confidence in teaching using SEs and about the prevalence of spatially rich approaches currently being used in post-primary mathematics lessons in Ireland. The next steps in this research which focuses on Strategy 2 will be to develop a KTF for mathematics and then to collaborate with post-primary teachers in the development,

teaching and assessment of spatially rich post-primary mathematics lessons to understand how to effectively use SEs and other supports to harness untapped potential of SR to improve the teaching and learning of mathematics.

References

- Bishop, A. J. (1980). Spatial abilities and mathematics education—A review. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 11(3), 257-269.
- Casey, B. (2004). Mathematics problem-solving adventures: A language-arts-based supplementary series for early childhood that focuses on spatial sense. Engaging young children in mathematics: *Standards for Early Childhood Mathematics Education*, 377-389.
- Clerkin, A., Perkins, R and Cunningham, R. (2016). TIMSS 2015 Mathematics and Science In Ireland: In Primary And Post-Primary Schools. *Educational Research Centre*
- Cheng, Y. L., & Mix, K. S. (2014). Spatial training improves children's mathematics ability. *Journal of Cognition and Development*, 15(1), 2–11.
- Diezmann, C. M., & Lowrie, T. (2012). Learning to think spatially: What do students ‘see’ in numeracy test items? *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 10(6), 1469-1490.
- Frick, A. (2019). Spatial transformation abilities and their relation to later mathematics performance. *Psychological Research*, 83, 1465–1484.
- Gagnier, K. M., & Fisher, K. R. (2020). Unpacking the Black Box of Translation: A framework for infusing spatial thinking into curricula. *Cognitive Research: Principles and Implications*, 5(1), 29.
- Giofrè, D., Mammarella, I. C., Ronconi, L., & Cornoldi, C. (2013). Visuospatial working memory in intuitive geometry, and in academic achievement in geometry. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 23, 114-122.
- Halpern, D. F. (2000). *Sex differences in cognitive abilities* (3rd ed.). Mahwah: Erlbaum.
- Harris, D., Lowrie, T., Logan, T., & Hegarty, M. (2021). Spatial reasoning, mathematics, and gender: Do spatial constructs differ in their contribution to performance? *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 91(1),
- Hawes, Z., Ansari, D. (2020). What explains the relationship between spatial and mathematical skills? A review of evidence from brain and behavior. *Psychonomic Bulletin and Review* 27, 465–482 (2020).
- Hembree, R. (1992), “Experiments and relational studies in problem solving: A meta-analysis”, *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, Vol. 23, pp. 242-289
- Jones, K. (2002), Issues in the Teaching and Learning of Geometry. In: Linda Haggarty (Ed), *Aspects of Teaching Secondary Mathematics: perspectives on practice*. London: Routledge Falmer. Chapter 8.

- Lowrie T., Logan T. (2018) The Interaction Between Spatial Reasoning Constructs and Mathematics Understandings in Elementary Classrooms. In: Mix K., Battista M. (eds) *Visualizing Mathematics. Research in Mathematics Education*. Springer, Cham.
- MacFarlane-Smith, I. (1964) *Spatial Ability: its educational and social significance*. London: University of London Press.
- NRC (2006). Learning to think spatially: GIS as a support system in the K–12 curriculum. Washington, DC: National Academic Press.
- NCCA (2015). Junior Key Skills. Department of Education and Skills
- NCCA (2017). Junior Cycle Mathematics. Department of Education and Skills
- National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (2000). *Principals and Standards for School Mathematics*, National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, Reston, VA.
- Newcombe, N. (2017). Harnessing spatial thinking to support stem learning. *OECD Education Working Paper* No. 161
- Newcombe, N., Booth, J., & Gunderson, E. (2019). Spatial Skills, Reasoning, and Mathematics. In J. Dunlosky & K. Rawson (Eds.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Cognition and Education* (Cambridge Handbooks in Psychology, pp. 100-123). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ontario Ministry of Education. (2014). Paying Attention to Spatial Reasoning, K-12 Support Document for Paying Attention to Mathematics Education. Queen’s Printer for Ontario.
- Pantziara, M., A. Gagatsis and I. Elia (2009), “Using diagrams as tools for the solution of non-routine mathematical problems”, *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, Vol. 72/1, pp. 39-60. Unclassified
- PDST (2021). Retrieved online at <https://www.projectmaths.ie/for-teachers/digital-learning/learn-to-use-geogebra/>. Accessed July 5th 2021(Newcombe, 2017)
- Perkins, R. & Clerkin A. (2020). TIMSS 2019 Ireland’s results in mathematics and science. *Educational Research Centre* (ERC).
- Reilly, D., Neumann, D. L., & Andrews, G. (2017). Gender differences in spatial ability: Implications for STEM education and approaches to reducing the gender gap for parents and educators. In *Visual-spatial Ability in STEM Education* (pp. 195-224). Springer, Cham.
- Sorby, S., Veurink, N., & Streiner, S. (2018). Does spatial skills instruction improve STEM outcomes? The answer is ‘yes’. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 67, 209-222.
- Syahputra, E. (2013). Increasing Spatial Ability of Students through the Application of Realistic Mathematics Learning. Yogyakarta: *Cakrawala Journal*. November 2013.